

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

D2.6 TOOLS AND SIMULATION MODELS FOR TREE AND CROP PRODUCTIVITY

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1	Context	3
2	Summary of activities	3
3	Detailed presentation of work done and next steps for each tool/topic	10
3.1	AgroforestAR: a tool to help design agroforestry systems with Augmented Reality	10
3.2	Dataset of crop and wood production in AFS	11
3.3	DENTRO: shrub and tree species adaptation in a changing climate	12
3.4	DECIDUOUS: fruit tree variety and rootstock selection	15
3.5	ShadeTreeAdvice: local ecological knowledge for tree selection	16
3.6	AgroforesTreeAdvice: combining heterogeneous knowledge resources for tree species selection	17

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WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

3.7	Agroforestry Flanders climate adaptation factsheet	19
3.8	Field trial of tree varieties: late budding walnut varieties in agroforestry systems	20
3.9	Field trial of crop varieties: an artificial shade trial	21
3.10	metAlsafe: metamodeling of Hi-sAFe to build a DSS for Agroforestry System Design	22
3.11	DEXiAF: a multicriteria assessment of the sustainability of agroforestry systems	23
3.12	Hi-sAFe: a tree-crop mechanistic model for temperate agroforestry systems	24
3.13	VOC'tool: characterising the chemical landscape and its effect on pests and beneficial arthropods	25
3.14	CarboCatch: validating carbon certificates in agroforestry	25
3.15	SCOPE: Remote sensing products to advance AF modelling	26
4	Acknowledgements	29
5	References	29

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WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

1 Context

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 - June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high-quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Our goal is to provide the main actor groups with tools answering their needs, in particular digital tools. The three actors' groups that are targeted by DigitAF are:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry-related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing AFS and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at the farm-level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries of AF products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of AFS, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of AF in clear and accessible terms.

This report is relevant for the second stakeholders' group. It contains a report on the activities aiming at **making models and tools for tree and crop productivity more practice-oriented towards end-users** (farmers and advisers), performed between January 2024 (date of submission of the first report on tools and simulation models for tree and crop productivity, [D2.5](#)) and July 2025. It is the final deliverable for task 2.2 "Assess, predict and optimize tree and crop performance of agroforestry". We first list the tools that have been developed or improved during these activities, and summarize the timeframe and deviations from the initial plan, as well as plans for dissemination and exploitation. Then we present, for each tool/model, the detailed activities, highlighting the improvements to (i) model/tool features (new functionalities), (ii) model/tool FAIRness and (iii) dissemination activities and eventual exploitation.

2 Summary of activities

DigitAF WP2 aimed to provide practitioners and farm advisors with tools for optimising agroforestry design and management. Within this WP, T2.2 aimed at developing/improving tools (digital or otherwise) to assess, predict and optimize tree and crop performance within agroforestry systems. This report organizes these tools following the idealized journey that a farmer would follow, going from agroforestry adoption, to agroforestry design, management, and finally commercialization of agroforestry products and services (Figure 1). For agroforestry adoption, we improved the smartphone/tablet app AgroforestAR, which allows visualising, through augmented reality, the future view of an agroforestry system directly in a farmer's field, to help farmers as well as the public envision what agroforestry is. Of course, virtual trees are less convincing than real trees, so we also developed demonstration plots (and published videos of these plots). We also measured tree and crop performance of experimental plots to provide quantitative data that help farmers decide whether to adopt agroforestry. At the beginning of the project, we performed a stakeholders' survey to identify the needs of farmers. The results of this survey highlighted the need of farmers for decision support tools for tree species choice; therefore, we developed several tree species selection tools, adapted to different use cases (climate zone, type of agroforestry): DENTRO, DECIDUOUS, ShadeTreeAdvice and AgroforesTreeAdvice. We also considered within-species variability, and performed field trials to

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

screen different tree and crop varieties for their suitability in agroforestry systems. Spatial design is also a very important aspect of agroforestry system design, so we are developing a tool, called metAlsafe, to help farmers optimize spatial design both at the field scale (i.e. density of trees, within-row and between-row distances) and at the farm scale (i.e. in which field to plant trees). Farmers and advisors usually design innovative agroforestry systems iteratively, by running several iterations of the design-assessment loop. Therefore, we worked on ex ante assessment tools, which allow assessing a prototype system before implementing it. These tools are either in the form of mechanistic models (Hi-sAFe, WaNulCas) or qualitative models (DexiAF). We also plan to integrate spatial design tools and production of ecosystem service maps. Once a farmer has implemented agroforestry systems, they need to manage it, often relying on field observations to make informed decisions. As farmers often lack knowledge about tree management, we developed educational material for tree management. We also strive to develop a device that would allow characterising the olfactory landscape of an agroforestry plot, as perceived by insects (both pests and natural enemies). This would enable the implementation of push-pull strategies, considering agroforestry as an integrated pest management strategy. Finally, we aim to facilitate the commercialization of agroforestry products and services, for example, by facilitating the verification of carbon removals by agroforestry, in line with carbon certification schemes, thanks to the robust and easy-to-use CarboCatch tool. Less directly linked to farmers' needs, but hopefully useful for further optimization of agroforestry systems, we also performed some methodological developments on the processing of remote sensing data with the SCOPE model to parameterize agroforestry models.

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

Figure 1: Position, within the agroforestry journey of a farmer (grey arrows), of the different tools (bold black) for agroforestry system (AFS) optimization developed within DigitAF.

To provide a quick overview of what has already been done and what remains to be done to reach these goals, Table 1 synthesises the activities on all tools/trials, presenting the deviations (or not) compared to the initial plan outlined in year 1 of the project. Most developments proceeded according to plan, although for some tools, unexpected technical difficulties led to delays or the need to adapt the methodology. Conversely, some unforeseen opportunities lead to new developments for some tools.

Table 1: Deviations (or not) compared to D2.5 Plan for improvement of existing tools/models for tree and crop productivity

Model/tool/guideline	Improvements	Partners involved	D2.5 timeline	Current state
AgroforestAR	Developing prototype	INRAE, CIRAD	Sept 2024	Dec 2024 (V1) Oct 2025 (V2)
Demo plots	Setting up new demonstration plots	ILVO, UNIPI		Done

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

	Field visits Videos			Done done
Technico-economic references	Measurement of tree and crop performance	ILVO, UNIPI		Underway
DENTRO	Launch Dentre as a separate tool in “Agroforestry Planner” + Add extra modules (fruit and nut tree species & variety choice, Poplar cultivar choice)	ILVO	June 2025	Done
DECIDUOUS	Parameterization for France Translation into English Adaptation to other countries	GRAB, INRAE	Done in 2024 End of 2025 End of 2025	- Underway Underway
ShadeTreeAdvice	Cleaning of data Inserting into AFTA	CIRAD	Done Done	- -
AgroforesTreeAdvice	Development of GUI Insertion of existing tools ShadeTreeAdvice DENTRO DECIDUOUS SCSM Czech database JBOJP GoÖko Finnish tree DB UK tree database Swiss database Development of API Consolidation of data	INRAE	Done Done Done Done Done Sept 2024 -not planned -not planned -not planned Jan 2025 June 2025	- - - - - Sept 2024 Sept 2024 Sept 2024 Jan 2025 Underway Underway Underway
Dutch factsheet on tree choice in a changing climate	Translation to English	ILVO	October 2024	Done
Tree varieties trial		ILVO		Underway
Crop varieties trial		ILVO		Underway
metAlsafe	Developing a meta-model of HisAFe	INRAE	August 2025	Prototype available
DEXIAF	Testing the tool with mature AF plots Testing the tool in 2 Living Labs	INRAE, GRAB, UniLaSalle, Living Labs	End of 2024 -not planned	Done End of 2025
Hi-sAFe	CO2 effect Cavitation (comparing with SUREAU) Making the code open-source	INRAE	Done August 2024 Dec 2024	- Underway March 2025

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

WaNulCas	Comparison with Hi-sAFe	INRAE	Done	-
OneForest +combinatorial maps	Integration of spatial design tools and production of ecosystem service maps. Testing the tool with AF plots	INRAE	June 2026	Underway
Tree management Guide	Inventory of tools Stakeholder survey Analysis framework of local issues and resources for tree management Educational material for tree management	CIRAD	Done Done August 2024 August 2024	Done Done
BRNmOdel	Build GUI Parameterize new contexts	INRAE	July 2024 June 2025	Done Abandoned
VOCscope	Evaluation of the VOC capture tool by varying different parameters Bibliography to improve the tool Testing of a new adsorbent to capture VOC	ITEIPMAI (ACTA)	Aug 2025 -unexpected -unexpected	January 2025 April 2025 Underway
CarboCatch		UGENT	-not planned	
SCOPE	Provide site-specific parameters based on remotely sense products and processed by SCOPE model and assess the suitability to provide information for the optimization of tree-crop performance	UEx	June 2025	Underway

Most of these tools have been added to the DigitAF tool catalogue, and we have also implemented filtering of tools according to user needs (e.g. according to the user's position along the agroforestry journey and type of agroforestry system). Table 2 provides links to the tools and their code.

Table 2: Synthesis of the tools/DSS that have been developed, with their links to code and to the tool/app.

name	description	DigitAF work	date of release	URL for code	URL for tool	open-source
AgroforestAR	An augmented reality app to visualize the future aspect of agroforestry plots in the field	Increased number of available species	2025-10	NA	App download for iOS and Android	no

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

DENTRO	Tree species selection tool	Development in Python, increased number of available species, more user-friendly interface, etc.	2025-6	GitLab ILVO	Agroforestry DENTRO	yes
DECIDUOUS	Fruit trees (species/rootstock/variety) selection tool	French version finalized, English version pending, German/Czech versions expected)	2024-3		https://www.grab.fr/deciduous-page-principale/	yes
ShadeTreeAdvice	Tree species selection tool	Data cleaning and formatting	2023-11	gitLab	https://www.shadetreeadvice.org/	no
AgroforesTreeAdvice	An aggregator of tree species selection tools.	Development	2024-10	gitHub	INRAE Shiny server	yes
metAlsafe	An easy-to-run simplified version of Hi-sAFe	Development	not released yet	gitHub	not available yet	yes
DEXIAF	Multi-criteria ex ante assessment tool	English version finalized	2025-5		https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools/tool/dexiaf	yes
Hi-sAFe	3D plot-scale agroforestry model representing interactions between trees and crops for light, nitrogen, water and microclimate	Release of the code in open source	2025-03	gitHub	Website	yes
VOC'TOOL	the volatile organic compounds (VOCs) TOOL to characterize the aromatic landscape	Conception and still developing Tool	2025-07	NA	https://www.iteipmai.fr/projets-rd/71-projets/313-digitaf	NA
CarboCatch	An online user-friendly tool for modelling carbon sequestered in aboveground biomass using a combination of field data, satellite data, and artificial intelligence. The goal of the tool is to align with carbon certification schemes to provide a reliable estimate of carbon certificates from agroforestry systems. So far the tool has been tested for walnut tree in silvopastoral systems, and shows promising results.	Testing the tool with LL partners, sharing the field data (tree allometry) on Zenodo for other researchers to use	2024-12	NA	https://carbo-catch.space4good.com/accounts/login/?next=/dashboard/	no

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

Even if this is the final deliverable for task 2.2, some activities (tool improvement but also dissemination of experiment results, factsheets, ...) will continue in the last year of the DigitAF project. The strategy for disseminating the final outcomes will include presentations at conferences, demonstrations at agricultural fairs, and use in teaching activities, among other approaches (Table 3). This table also presents current and/or potential exploitation of the results of task 2.2, as well as the means to monitor its impact in the future. The detailed activities are then presented in the subsequent sections.

Table 3: Dissemination and exploitation activities performed/planned for each tool, and the means to monitor their impact in the future.

name	dissemination	exploitation	monitoring of impact
AgroforestAR	one presentation of the beta version at a stakeholder meeting (20250116), one expected poster in the World Congress on Agroforestry (October 2025)		App download stats from app stores will be used to monitor tool use
DENTRO	not available yet		NA
DECIDUOUS	webinars, press, mailing lists...	Deciduous has been used by farmers or advisors with nice feedback on its usability and utility.	Good feedback from farmers, users
ShadeTreeAdvice	scientific publications and conferences, presentations to practitioners	NA	NA
AgroforesTreeAdvice	One scientific publication. 4 presentations in conferences and stakeholders meetings (20231114, 20240527, 20250206, 20250311)+	There are plans to integrate the AgroforesTreeAdvice tool with other agroforestry design software such as RegenWorks	The SK8 team, which hosts the application, has chosen to develop a non-intrusive service, so the use of tracking tools is not foreseen. Therefore, there is no stats on app usage.
metAlsafe	One expected poster in the World Congress on Agroforestry (October 2025)		
DEXIAF	agricultural fair, conferences		
Hi-sAFe		the model will be used in the EELAP European project, it will be further developed (new versions for tropical agroforestry systems using Faidherbia, cocoa) within the GALILEO European project	It is too early to see an impact. The impact can be estimated by an expected increase in the number of new users. In the past (2018-2025), the average number of new users was 2.7 (+/-1.8) per month.
VOC'TOOL	not available yet		

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

Powerpoint and poster presented at conferences. Also a Dutch report which can be accessed on request.	Still looking for a suitable exploitation model, pilot with a real project developer needed	Needs more active users, pilot with real project developer needed
CarboCatch		

3 Detailed presentation of work done and next steps for each tool/topic

3.1 AgroforestAR: a tool to help design agroforestry systems with Augmented Reality

3.1.1 Tool improvement

AgroforestAR is a suite of modules to allow capturing the composition and configuration of an agroforestry system based on physical tokens such as those used in mock-ups used in design workshops, building a formal representation of the system, and finally visualizing the system in augmented reality (Lemière 2023). It was developed in a previous project, but it was just a library of different modules (capture, formalisation, visualisation), and it was not available as an app. In line with D2.5, in DigitAF, we developed a prototype to demonstrate the possibilities of augmented reality to communicate about agroforestry with farmers and the wider public. The first step was to transform the visualisation library into a stand-alone app (Figure 2 left). Then, we used a plant architecture software to generate realistic-looking models (Figure 1 right) of six different species of trees that are often used in agroforestry: service tree (*Cornus domestica*), wild cherry (*Prunus avium*), Aleppo pine (*Pinus halepensis*), black poplar (*Populus nigra*), walnut (*Juglans regia*), and olive tree (*Olea europaea*).

Figure 2: Improvements made to the AgroforestAR Augmented Reality tool: prototype with simplistic representations of trees (left) and first released version with realistic representations of trees (right)

3.1.2 Dissemination and exploitation

Agroforestry is gaining increasing attention from researchers and practitioners in temperate areas, but it remains a vague concept for most of the public. This is because the renewal of interest for agroforestry systems is quite recent, demonstration sites are rare, and trees are still young, and therefore not very visible. AgroforestAR aims to allow visualizing what an agroforestry system could look like on a given piece of land (including in your garden!). It uses the augmented reality capabilities already available in most smartphones, to superimpose, on the view seen by the phone's or tablet's camera, trees aligned along a line defined by the user by walking from one side of the piece of land to the other side. The user can then select the tree species and size, as well as different distances between tree lines and different distances between trees along the line. The user can choose between

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

four seasons, which will affect sun elevation, and for deciduous species also canopy leafiness, in order to visualize tree shade projection at different times of day. The app is freely available on Apple and Android app stores (Figure 3). To use it, stand at the bottom-left corner of the plot, open the app, “scan” the ground around you to detect the soil surface, and click on the dotted area where you want to plant the first tree. Then walk to the top-left corner of the plot, and click where you want to plant the last tree in the row. Four rows of trees are automatically placed to your right. This could be a valuable awareness-raising tool for the public, due to its simplicity of use and fun results.

Figure 3: QR codes for downloading the AgroforestAR augmented reality app on smartphones and tablets on the Android App Store (left) and the Apple App Store (right)

3.2 Dataset of crop and wood production in AFS

Since 2014 onwards, ILVO has been monitoring a set of alley cropping fields in Belgium to assess the production of both arable crops and woody biomass in temperate alley cropping systems. On a set of six fields, crop yield measurements are conducted every year to assess both yield and quality of the crops cultivated in the alleys between the tree rows. Sampled crops include maize, winter cereals and potato. The continuous measurements allow for the assessment of the effect of increasing tree size and, through the use of a transect approach, the impact of distance from the tree rows. The aforementioned set of six fields is part of a larger set of temperate alley cropping fields on which a selection of tree characteristics is monitored. The parameters studied include tree size (e.g. DBH, Height) and a selection of quality (e.g. branch-free stem) and vitality parameters.

3.2.1.1 FEATURE IMPROVEMENT

Within the DigitAf project, the above measurements were continued. This included both in-field measurements of arable crop production as well as laboratory analysis of the gathered crop samples. Analysis of the vast dataset on crop performance, developed over the past few years, required thorough statistical analysis. To facilitate in-depth analysis and discussion, an A1 publication was prepared within the DigitAf project and submitted to the scientific journal *Agroforestry Systems* (status June 2024: revisions submitted). To allow for a more efficient dissemination and wider use, all the gathered data were ordered into two separate datasets following the tidy data principles. The two resulting datasets, one focusing on the arable crop data and the other on the tree component were/will be made available via Zenodo and the DigitAf Data Catalogue.

3.2.1.2 FAIRNESS IMPROVEMENT

Whereas initially most of the gathered data (since 2014) were mainly stored locally, the DigitAf project allowed the structuring of the dataset and the thorough processing and analysis of the data. As such, the impact of tree presence on crop yield could be modelled and the results of this analysis were/will

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

be made available to the broader public. The structuring in Excel and online publication of the datasets increased visibility and accessibility, and their wider use, by e.g. other research institutions.

Besides the datasets, a range of relevant materials was also produced to support the project's outcomes. These included short videos showcasing the agroforestry experimental sites in Flanders, illustrating the design elements and ongoing monitoring processes. The videos give a visual understanding of the practical (monitoring) aspects of agroforestry systems, which is ideal for researchers and practitioners: [Experimental sites - Agroforestry](#)

3.2.1.3 DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION

Results of the data analysis on crop yield are/will be communicated through various channels (scientific journal, Zenodo¹, agroforestry manual of Agroforestry Flanders, website and newsletter of the consortium Agroforestry Flanders, ...). Therefore, various stakeholders will be reached, among others, researchers and model developers, farmers and the government.

Both the dataset on arable crop yield and quality² and the dataset on the studied tree parameters will be made available on Zenodo (with a unique DOI) and included in the DigitAf Data catalogue. Both datasets will be usable for modelling (e.g. calibration and/or validation) or other research purposes.

3.3 DENTRO: shrub and tree species adaptation in a changing climate

In recent years, a growing interest in agroforestry systems has been observed in Belgium and the Netherlands. Therefore, it is important to pay sufficient attention to the tree species selection process as this plays a major role in whether the agroforestry project is successful or not. Climate change causes longer periods of (long-term) drought or heavy rainfall which can affect tree growth. This is why it is important that tree species fit the farmer's field conditions and can handle well with (extreme) weather conditions occurring in the local region. This is why we developed DENTRO, a tree species selection tool of Agroforestry Flanders, in the first place. Now, we have improved DENTRO by, among other things, adding more tree species and parameters, including "climate scores" and translating the tool into English.

The objective of DENTRO is to guide users in selecting tree and shrub species that match the users' site conditions and goals. While using DENTRO, the user gains knowledge about tree characteristics, and the effect of a species' suitability to specific site and climatic conditions. At the end, the user can generate a summarizing report that compiles the selected species along with the relevant parameters. The latter is helpful for comparing different scenarios.

3.3.1 Feature improvement

Improve and enlarge the dataset

In the previous version of DENTRO, the dataset was called "DENTRO Tree Matrix" (EN) or "DENTRO Bomenmatrix" (NL). This dataset contained information about how ~80 tree species match certain relevant parameters, varying from abiotic conditions (e.g. soil, weather, light, etc.) to animals, objectives (e.g. wood/fruit/nut production and ecological function), feasibility (e.g. disease risks and planting material availability). These tree species were chosen as they were planted frequently in Flemish agroforestry systems. However, it would be interesting to add a wider range of tree species that can cope well with extreme weather events. As the KU Leuven published a study on climate trees, including a useful dataset containing 254 tree species (Desie et al., 2024), this dataset was merged with the Tree Matrix dataset. At the moment, DENTRO contains 334 species (incl. cultivars) combined.

¹ DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14192640

² DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10692760.

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

In this way, the (international) end user can find a broader range of tree species for their agroforestry project. Additionally, more parameters were added such as the “climate score”. The climate score is a combined assessment of a species’ suitability under different climate scenarios, the overall trend across those scenarios, and expert knowledge based on literature and interviews (Desie et al., 2024).

Improve the interface

Initially, DENTRO’s interface was not optimal, mainly due to the long page load times, the functionality (i.e. unnecessary clicks, improving the scoring scale, and adding English), and the outdated lay-out. Switching to Python improved overall tool performance in different ways.

Tool performance

The previous version of DENTRO was developed in Oracle Apex. Oracle Apex is a low-code development platform that enables to build web applications on Oracle databases. However, researchers or programmers did not have experience with Oracle at ILVO, making the tool difficult to maintain/reuse. This is why we have decided to switch to Python, a general-purpose programming language, instead. Accordingly, DENTRO was placed on ILVO’s server, whereas the previous version was placed on Soil Service Belgium’s server. Now, DENTRO demonstrates a minimal delay between request and response (low latency) and optimized performance, so that the end user can experience fast page load times.

Tool functionality

The tool developers have analysed how the number of clicks can be minimized. In the old version (Figure X.), users had to click “next” to access each filter step, making it incompatible to apply multiple filters at once and requiring up to seven steps to complete the process. This not only slowed down the workflow but also made the user experience inefficient. In addition, users were also required to select all or some tree species before they could proceed, which seemed unnecessary from a tool developer’s point of view. The new interface resolves these issues by adjusting the layout including displaying all filters neatly in a left-hand menu (Figure Y.). For a quicker and more intuitive filtering experience, a green guiding box with filters was also placed at the top. Now, the user can apply multiple filters at once and instantly see the remaining species available for selection.

Secondly, the scoring system was modified to improve tool functionality. The original 7-point scale (- very unsuitable, - unsuitable, (-) slightly unsuitable, + - neutral, (+) slightly suitable, + suitable, ++ very suitable) seemed too detailed. Moreover, using symbols in the dataset proved impractical, so we replaced them with numeric values, and decided to leave the numbers in the front-end as well. To simplify data collection and facilitate user interpretation in the future, we merged similar categories. For instance, combining scores [- and (-)] and [(+) and +] resulting in a 5-point scale: 1. very unsuitable, 2. (slightly) unsuitable, 3. neutral, 4. (slightly) suitable, 5. very suitable. We have also added a new feature to filter based on the scoring system. In the old version, users could only sort individual parameters in ascending or descending order – similar to how you would filter a column in Excel. Now, users can adjust the selection strictness using a slider (left menu), encompassing all parameters. This

allows a more precise match between the tree species and the users' to adjust the selection strictness from 1 (not strict; unsuitable species are included) to 5 (strict; only very suitable species are included), allowing the user to more specifically find trees matching the environment.

Thirdly, the tool developers have translated the interface into English. This makes sure that translations are carried out more precisely compared to adding a translator plug-in for the front-end. Users can easily switch between Dutch and English by clicking on resp. "NL" or "EN" in the top right. Once the language has a light green background colour, it is selected (e.g., EN was selected in Figure Y). Regarding the back-end, the code was written in English, allowing international researchers to understand the code and facilitating tool interoperability.

Lay-out improvement

The colour scheme was updated from a red-to-green colour gradient (Figure 4) to a modern look with white and green tones (Figure 5). Previously, a scoring system was applied using a scale ranging from - to +, combined with different intensities of background colours (red is unsuitable and green is suitable). The current version has a new colour scheme which is less distracting (the background colouring of scores was removed), and matches ILVO's colour scheme.

Figure 4: The interface of the previous version of DENTRO – sometimes referred as 'Tree Matrix'

Figure 5: The new interface of DENTRO

3.3.2 FAIRness improvement

Findability was not improved as the new link to DENTRO will replace the old link on the Agroforestry Planner and on the DigitAF Tool Catalogue. DENTRO was an open-access tool, and the new version will remain an open-access tool as well. As the web tool is now based on Python code (see previous section, this would make the dataset more interoperable in the future by e.g. using APIs. Lastly, the new dataset can be reused in other tree species selection tools, such as AgroforestryAdvice or other tools hosted at the Agroforestry Planner.

3.3.3 Dissemination and exploitation

DENTRO is online and can be accessed through: [Agroforestry DENTRO](#). The dataset was uploaded on Community Agroforestry Flanders at Zenodo, for which access can be requested: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15703911>. The next steps are to announce it in the newsletter of Agroforestry Vlaanderen. The next steps are to replace the old link to the Tree Matrix by the new DENTRO web tool at the Agroforestry Planner, and at the DigitAF Tool Catalogue.

3.4 DECIDUOUS: fruit tree variety and rootstock selection

Deciduous tool has been designed for farmers willing to add fruit trees in their plots but do not have the appropriate knowledge to make optimal choices: which fruit species? Which rootstock? Which varieties? Information online might not be so easy to find and to use. A collaboration between GRAB and INRAE allowed developing an easy-to-use tool using Shinyapp. The farmer/user is presented with a minimal number of questions concerning mainly (i) the time and period of workforce availability, (ii) the type of soil of the plot, (iii) the risk of frost in the area. Then the tool computes a score of suitability for a list of species and rootstocks, allowing the user to choose the most adapted to their conditions. At the beginning of DigitAF, a first prototype of the tool was available only in French language. After translation into English, the tool was presented to farmers in the DigitAF Living Labs and three of them have expressed interest in this tool: Germany, Czech Republic, Belgium. Partners in these countries are currently working on national content in order to provide a national version with local data/varieties.

3.4.1 Feature improvement

The French version of Deciduous tool has been finalized and released in spring 2024.

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

The tool itself can be accessed directly through a ShinyApp :

https://paut-et-al.shinyapps.io/OAD_AF_Fruits

This tool has also been integrated in a digital guidebook to support and help user with a lot of technical information on fruit species, rootstocks, varieties :

<https://www.grab.fr/deciduous-page-principale>

The English version based on French data will be made available by the end of 2025, after performing some final checks.

3.4.2 FAIRness improvement

Deciduous has been integrated in the Digitaf catalogue, and its findability has therefore been increased. The English version will also improve its FAIR scoring.

FAIRness score v1.0

3.4.3 Dissemination and exploitation

The Deciduous tool should be developed in Germany and Czech Republic, after it has been adapted to national conditions and fruit varieties especially.

The French version has been widely advertised since its release and has been used with success and enthusiasm by farmers, teachers or advisors.

3.5 ShadeTreeAdvice: local ecological knowledge for tree selection

The ShadeTreeAdvice online tool was developed to aid farmers in selecting appropriate shade tree species by leveraging local ecological knowledge (<https://www.shadetreeadvice.org>). Its database relies on interviews gathered from experienced farmers, considered as local experts, to inform about the impacts of different shade tree species on the main crop performances and the provision of ecosystem services. Wherever a local database is available (building a local database requires investigating the local ecological knowledge in the area), farmers can select their crop of interest and choose the attributes or ecosystem services that are most important to them. The tool then displays advised tree species on a graph, with the most suitable species scoring the highest and shown at the top. The graph uses colors to indicate how each tree performs for each of the selected attributes, making it easier for farmers to make informed decisions.

Over five years between 2016 and 2024, ten studies following the associated ShadeTreeAdvice methodology were conducted (in order to build local databases) in various coffee and cocoa growing regions across Africa, Asia, and Central America. The results of these studies were uploaded to the decision support tool, which is accessible to farmers and, most importantly, to extension services. This tool not only stimulates the use of shade trees but also emphasizes the importance of diversifying plantations according to local conditions, farmers' constraints and objectives.

3.5.1 Feature improvement

The ShadeTreeAdvice tool is continuously evolving and improving through ongoing studies. Since the inception of Digitaf, a new study from Columbia has been validated (with a scientific publication: <https://doi.org/10.19182/bft2025.362.a37432>) and added to the tool, enriching the tool's database.

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

Additionally, two more studies are currently underway in Ivory Coast and Cameroon. These ongoing efforts expand the tool's geographic scope, ensuring that it remains dynamic and provides farmers and extension services with relevant and up-to-date information.

Furthermore, a concerted effort has been made with the DigitAF partners to adopt a unified typology for the criteria of tree species selection. Previously, some redundancies and inconsistencies existed due to the tool's local development: each local study followed a common methodology with clear steps to gather local ecological knowledge, but lacked a theoretical canvas to organise the results. By integrating the existing local databases into this new unified typology, significant progress has been made in detecting inconsistencies and weaknesses of the previous local databases. This process involved reorganizing the set of criteria for tree species selection, based on response-traits (adaptation to local conditions) and effect-traits (effectiveness at realizing a function or at providing ecosystem service), and cleaning up the database, including standardizing the Latin names of tree species. Not all criteria could be modified to fit in the new typology at this late stage, nonetheless the new typology provides a structured canvas for future work, accommodating both local specificities and the global need for data uniformization. This effort was part of a broader initiative to develop a common tool, AgroforestTreeAdvice. The criteria and computation of the score will depend on the tool, but the unified typology ensures a more consistent approach to tree species selection.

3.5.2 Dissemination and exploitation

The ShadeTreeAdvice tool is readily accessible online at <https://www.shadetreeadvice.com>. While the current design is more tailored to extension services (currently the main users) than to smallholder farmers, efforts are underway to make the tool more attractive and more user-friendly for smallholder farmers as well. In particular, one notable initiative is the ongoing trial in China to reprogram ShadeTreeAdvice as an app and integrate it within WeChat (the leading social network in China, widely used by all the population including farmers). This app will be fully translated into Chinese, making it more accessible to local farmers, and it will only contain the local database on coffee agroforestry in Yunnan Province. This trial aims to provide Chinese farmers with direct and easy access to the tool and will offer valuable insights and lessons to improve the user interface of the general tool.

3.6 AgroforestTreeAdvice: combining heterogeneous knowledge resources for tree species selection

Selecting the right tree species is a crucial step in designing sustainable and effective agroforestry systems. To support this process, several decision support systems (DSS) have been developed in various countries to help farmers and advisors choose appropriate species. However, these tools are often limited in reach—typically used only within the country where they were created—and tend to focus on different aspects of adaptation to local conditions or achieving specific farming objectives. Our objective was to create a unified framework to combine the knowledge present in these tools.

3.6.1 Feature improvement

In DigitAF, we set up a working group on tree species selection to join efforts in order to develop a common framework in which these tools could all fit. The objectives were twofold: (i) to compile and organize the knowledge embedded in existing tree selection tools, and (ii) to offer an intuitive, user-friendly graphical interface — AgroforestTreeAdvice. This tool allows users to input local parameters such as soil type, climate, biotic factors, and farm-level or socio-economic constraints, alongside

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

production goals (e.g., timber, fruits) and ecosystem service objectives (e.g., soil conservation, carbon storage). The unified system successfully integrates ten existing agroforestry DSS.

to increase their i) findability (all tools are gathered in the same place), ii) accessibility (a common interface allows users to query the tools with interfaces having the same look and feel), and iii) interoperability (API requests can be used to query all tools).

Our hypothesis was that all tree selection tools work by matching tree traits to selection criteria defined by the user in order to provide a suitability score for each tree species, and that the selection criteria, although being different between different tools, could be organised in a structured way to make comparisons between tools possible. We considered that tree suitability depends on i) adaptation to local conditions and ii) efficiency at providing the desired benefits (tree products and/or ecosystem services (ES)). Based on the trait-function-service framework (Violle et al. 2007), we organized the data according to two types of tree traits: response traits (causing the response of the tree to its environment, and so driving its adaptation to local conditions) and effect traits (allowing the tree to perform functions leading to the production of ES, e.g. fulfilling the farmer's objectives). Criteria linked to the provision of ES (and therefore the matching effect traits) were organized following the CICES 5.1 classification (Haines-Young and Potschin 2018) at the highest levels, and subsequent levels were added when more details were needed (e.g. distinguishing between different uses of wood). In the absence of an internationally recognized classification of criteria linked to the adaptation to local conditions, these criteria were organized as adaptation to soil, climate, biotic context, constraints at plot scale, constraints at farm scale and constraints at socio-economic level. As for ES, we classified these criteria in a hierarchical manner, allowing different levels of detail according to the focus of each tool. Finally, we developed a shiny app using this common framework to interface with several tree selection tools.

3.6.2 FAIRness improvement

The interface was built with FAIR principles at its heart. It improves the initial tools (i) findability by centralizing them in one location, (ii) accessibility through a standardized and user-friendly interface, (iii) interoperability by enabling API-based queries across all tools, and (iv) reusability for future DSS development. AgroforesTreeAdvice was assessed for FAIRness using the FAIRness self-assessment tool developed within the DigitAF project (https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools/fairness_self_assessment). This tool gave us the score of AgroforesTreeAdvice on the four aspects of FAIRness: Findability: 67%, Accessibility: 80%, Interoperability: 63% and Reusability: 75%. These numbers show the improvement in FAIRness compared to the initial tools (Table 4).

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

Table 4 : FAIRness assessment score of the previously existing tools or data sheets. Please note that the criteria for data and tools FAIRness are not exactly the same, so FAIRness scores of data (in italics) and tools cannot be compared. Some tools have significantly progressed in terms of FAIRness during the process of this work, in which case the values in brackets are the most recent values.

Tool	F	A	I	R
Czech (data)	<i>0</i>	<i>25</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>17</i>
DECIDUOUS	100 [100]	40 [60]	40 [50]	0 [63]
GoÖko	100	77	60	63
DENTRO (data)	65	75	10	83
JBOJP	33	55	24	13
SCSM ^a	-	-	-	-
STA	33	40	30	50
FTSDB (data)	<i>67</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>50</i>	<i>67</i>
AgroforesTreeAdvice	67	80	63	75

^a: SCSM is not a standalone tool, but it is data belonging to a larger software, so it was not assessed individually

3.6.3 Dissemination and exploitation

The tool was tested in three countries, which allowed collecting user feedback, highlighting the tool's benefits and outlining next steps toward further harmonization of agroforestry databases. The tool was also presented in a scientific publication ([Gosme et al 2025](#)) and presented in several conferences and professional symposiums for farmers and advisors.

Our ambition for AgroforesTreeAdvice is to make it the central hub for interoperability of all tree species selection tools for agroforestry, providing the underlying information (database and model) in a homogenized way, allowing interoperability with other tools facilitating agroforestry system design and management. Several commercial advisory tools for farmers (e.g. RegenWorks, LandFiles and FarmTree) have expressed interest in using this resource.

3.7 Agroforestry Flanders climate adaptation factsheet

In this factsheet, a selection of tree species that are assumed to be suitable for cultivation in Flemish AFS under changing climatic conditions is presented and discussed. Thereby, focus lies on tree species which can develop a branch-free stem and which can be used for production of high-value wood (e.g. veneer, construction wood). Included species are: *Acer campestre*, *Acer platanoides*, *Carpinus betulus*, *Castanea sativa*, *Juglans spp.*, *Malus sylvestris*, *Populus spp.*, *Pyrus pyraster*, *Quercus petraea*, *Quercus robur*, *Sorbus aucuparia*, *Sorbus torminalis*, *Tilia cordata* and *Tilia platyphyllos*. For all included species, their resistance to drought and heat waves is indicated, as well as their required growing conditions and applications for the wood they produce.

3.7.1 Feature improvement

The current version of the factsheet is only available in Dutch and on the (Flemish) website [Home - Agroforestry](#). Within the DigitAf project, the factsheet will be translated into English by ILVO and made accessible via the DigitAf project website.

3.7.2 FAIRness improvement

By translating the factsheet into English and including it in the DigitAF catalogue FAIRness was improved. In particular, the findability and accessibility increased from 33% to 67% and 30% to 40%, respectively, using the Agroforestry Tools FAIRness Self-Assessment calculator.

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

3.7.3 Dissemination and exploitation

The current Flemish version of the factsheet will remain available on the website [Home - Agroforestry](#), in addition, the English version will be added to the DigitAf Tools, Data and Projects Catalogue.

3.8 Field trial of tree varieties: late budding walnut varieties in agroforestry systems

In temperate regions such as Flanders and the Netherlands, shade competition poses a significant challenge in agroforestry systems. In this context, walnut (*Juglans regia*) trees are considered suitable partners for these systems, as their bud break occurs relatively late compared to other tree species. However, there is a large range of bud break amongst walnut trees. To address this issue, a long-term trial has been initiated to evaluate the potential of very late-budding walnut (LUW) varieties. These varieties, which break bud after mid-May, reduce the frost damage risk and minimize shading pressure on intercrops due to their delayed leaf (and flower) development. Furthermore, they are hypothesized to be more resistant to pests and disease, likely due to their shorter exposure period in critical periods.

The advantages of LUW varieties are expected to become even more relevant under changing climate conditions. As warmer springs cause earlier bud break, thereby increasing vulnerability of reproductive organs to late frosts, LUW trees offer a resilient alternative. Their delayed development may also help mitigate the effects of shifting pest and disease dynamics associated with climate change.

3.8.1 LUW varieties

While growers and nut experts have suggested the benefits of late budding, LUW varieties are not yet commercially available. Therefore, 19 promising LUW varieties were selected and propagated from scions collected in Flanders and the Netherlands. These were planted across five experimental sites in Flanders and one in the Netherlands during the winter of 2020–2021, alongside several commonly used control varieties.

The trial aims to assess phenology, flowering, disease susceptibility, growth, and eventually nut yield and quality. Monitoring over the first three years (2021–2023) confirmed that LUW varieties consistently bud later than controls, with some not leafing out until early June. This timing places them safely beyond the typical frost risk period (before May 15), offering a clear advantage in spring frost-prone climates. Flowering observations revealed that LUW trees also tend to flower later, thereby further reducing frost risk during reproductive stages. Growth measurements indicate successful establishment across sites, though differences between varieties are not yet conclusive. Preliminary data suggest LUW trees may be less susceptible to foliar diseases and pests.

Figure 6: spring frost damage on developing walnut leaves (photo taken on 19/04/2022).

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

This ongoing trial is expected to yield valuable insights into the suitability of LUW varieties for agroforestry, particularly in terms of resilience, productivity, and compatibility with intercrops. Future monitoring will focus on nut yield, quality, and long-term tree health to guide variety selection for sustainable agroforestry systems.

3.8.2 Dissemination and exploitation

Results of the LUW trial (2021 – 2023) are compiled in a technical report available through the website www.agroforestryvlaanderen.be. Results from 2024 and beyond will be analyzed under the [PRO-NOOT](#) project and made public in due course. The results of the LUW trials will allow farmers and other stakeholders to select suitable varieties for use in agroforestry systems, thereby increasing the productivity of these systems.

3.9 Field trial of crop varieties: an artificial shade trial

In Northwestern Europe, light is probably the most critical limiting resource for crops in the understory, and most agronomic studies show a systematic reduction in final yield as shade increases. While this effect itself has been thoroughly evaluated in previous research for a range of arable crop species, through both empirical studies and modelling work, further work is needed to gain practical insights into how the composition of agroforestry systems can be adapted to reduce this negative effect of shading. An important aspect in this search is the selection of adapted crop species and varieties.

3.9.1.1 FEATURE IMPROVEMENT

In a long-term experimental setup, an artificial shade structure was installed at ILVO, mimicking a mature agroforestry system by using military camouflage netting to provide discontinuous light throughout the day (based on Artru et al. 2017). The construction was made of vertical concrete poles with a height of 3,5m and with a metal crossbeam of 3m long attached to the top of the poles. These poles are installed in a straight row of 110m on the field, approximately North-South oriented, with the camouflage netting fixed on top of the crossbeams (Fig. 7). In the alleys East and West from this construction, nine crop plots of 12m long (along the row of poles) were installed, enabling to evaluate three crop treatments in three replicates per season. The light reduction was monitored at different positions in the field, East and West, from the row of poles, using pyranometers. At the same positions, air humidity and temperature, soil water content, soil temperature, and soil water potential are also assessed. Within the DigitAf project, we evaluated the impact of the partial shade conditions on crop productivity starting from the growth season of 2022. From 2022 to 2024 grass-clover mixtures were present in the trial. In the summer of 2025, a new similar construction was installed on another one of ILVO's arable experimental fields. A similar experimental design will be used, this time assessing the impact on a selection of winter wheat varieties.

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

Figure 7: artificial shade trial with testing of grass-clover mixtures at ILVO

3.9.2 Dissemination and exploitation

The results of the grass-clover mixture are currently being analysed and compiled into a manuscript for an A1 publication (current status: in preparation). However, preliminary results are already made available via the website https://ilvo.vlaanderen.be/uploads/documents/Agroforestry/AF2025_L3-2_Rapport_Schaduwproef-grasklaver_VLAI0-AF2025.pdfw and in the agroforestry manual³ written by Agroforestry Flanders. The results of both trials on grass-clover and winter wheat will enable farmers and other stakeholders to select suitable cultivars for use in agroforestry systems, thereby enhancing the productivity of these systems.

3.10 metAIsafe: metamodeling of Hi-sAFe to build a DSS for Agroforestry System Design

3.10.1 Model creation

Due to the scarcity of experimental data on agroforestry systems, mechanistic soil-crop models are necessary to predict the performance of agroforestry (AF) systems in a range of situations and in particular under a changing climate. However, they are rarely used as a decision support system for cropping system design by farmers or farm advisors, because they are quite difficult to parameterize for a given situation, and they are sometimes computer-intensive, meaning they cannot be used in real-time as a DSS. Our objective is to build a metamodel to support farmers' decisions (AF or not AF, choice of plot, AF spatial design), based on a statistical approximation of a mechanistic model.

The first step was to perform a sensitivity analysis of an AF model, to select the variables on which the meta-model will be built. We used the Hi-sAFe model because it is a very detailed tree and crop growth and production model, allowing us to take into account competitions between trees and crops for light, water and nutrients, as well as some effects on the microclimate. We performed a sensitivity analysis of tree and crop yield in a Mediterranean cereal-walnut alley cropping system as a case study.

³ DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13907299.

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

The tested input variables were climate change (past, present, future), soil (water table depth, stoniness), cropping system (wheat monocrop, maize monocrop, wheat-maize rotation), tree density, tree root pruning.

The results show that stone content had a major effect on both tree and crop yield, so much so that neither the crop nor the tree grew well in the 70% stone condition. Excluding the data from the highly stony soil, the relative importance of the other inputs depended on the output variable and varied with system age. For tree yield, tree density has the highest effect during the whole simulation (with the highest yield for intermediate density), climate change was the second most important determinant of tree yield, while water table had an impact only for trees of intermediate ages. For crop yield, the main determinant was crop species (the yield of maize was higher than wheat), followed by period for wheat (lower yield in the past) and the presence of trees for maize (lower yield in agroforestry). The relative yield of maize ranged from 0.82 to 0.94, was lowest for the intermediate tree density (100 trees/ha) in particular with 30% of stones. For the lowest and highest tree densities (50, 200 trees/ha), the relative yield of maize is predicted to increase in the future compared to the past and present climate. The relative yield of wheat ranged from 0.85 to 0.98; it was lowest for the past climate and then was lower for 100 trees/ha than for 50 and 200 trees/ha. Contrary to maize, the relative yield of wheat is predicted to decrease in the future compared to the present.

In conclusion, some variables had a small effect on yield of both tree and crop, and can be neglected in the future decision support system: rotation (it can be simplified into presence of wheat), tree root pruning, water table depth (it only had a transient effect on tree yield), stone content when it is below a threshold that remains to be determined. Tree density had a non-linear impact, and future studies are needed to better untangle the effects of distance between tree rows vs distance between trees within the rows. Finally, climate change had a complex impact that varied according to the species (maize, wheat, walnut) and conditions, so advice regarding decisions under one climate might not be generalizable to other climates.

After this sensitivity analysis, we ran new simulations on a wider set of conditions (in particular, different types of soil and different climatic zones in France) and included more output variables. These results are currently being analysed, and the outputs will be treated to generate the meta-model. In parallel, we are developing a user interface to make the results accessible to farmers and advisors. This interface will propose two modes: a “beginner mode”, where the user describes the conditions of their farm (climate, soil) and can run and compare scenarios (system spatial design, crop choice). An “advanced mode” will allow using the metamodel in a reverse way: instead of running a user-defined scenario, the model will be used to analyse the sensitivity of the model to “free” variables, within the set of constrained variables. This will be used as a teaching tool to help users hierarchize the importance of different agronomical levers and to identify, as a function of the farmer’s objectives, the best plot in their farm to perform agroforestry and the associated optimal design.

3.10.2 Dissemination and exploitation

Since the tool does not yet exist, the FAIRness hasn’t been evaluated yet, and no dissemination activity has been done yet. However, the initial sensitivity analysis will be presented as a poster at the World Congress on Agroforestry in Rwanda in October 2025.

3.11 DEXiAF: a multicriteria assessment of the sustainability of agroforestry systems

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

The DEXIAF tool is developed by INRAE with Grab and other partners. It aims at assessing multi-criteria sustainability of a new agroforestry plot before it's planted, in order to improve it and avoid failures. It is using DEXI technology, meaning decomposing a complex situation into simpler ones that can be sorted and weighed.

It has now been added to the catalogue and made available to all users :

https://euraf.github.io/AF_FAIRness/tools/tool/dexiaf

A demonstration video has also been released early in 2025, with subtitles available :

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9JQwW30WZms>

FAIRness score remains rather low for DEXIAF as the DEXI technology requires some practice.

FAIRness score v1.0

DEXIAF will be displayed in one or several Living Labs of the project during the last year.

It has been presented by INRAE at an international Conference. It will also be presented during a French national event on multi-criteria assessment in [September 2025](#).

3.12 Hi-sAFe: a tree-crop mechanistic model for temperate agroforestry systems

Hi-sAFe (Dupraz et al. 2019) is a daily time-step, 3D, soil-crop-tree model. It predicts crop and tree growth and yield, as well as some environmental performances, as a function of pedoclimatic conditions and tree and crop management, taking into account tree-crop competition for light, water and nitrogen. In the current reporting period,

3.12.1 Model improvement

a) Improving the ability to represent the effect of agroforestry on the heat wave resilience of crops

The effect of water stress in plants is currently represented in the model by stress indices that reduce physiological processes, but do not kill the plant, allowing it to recover after the heat wave. Episodes of extreme drought might make this an oversimplification. We used the Sureau plant hydraulic model (Cochard et al. 2021) and compared its outputs to **Hi-sAFe's** outputs, in "normal" conditions (i.e. absence of heat wave) and during heat waves, on plant water potential, LAI, potential evapotranspiration, actual evapotranspiration and soil predawn water potential. We faced several difficulties in terms of model coupling (discrepancies in timesteps and in state variables). Once the models were coupled (i.e. microclimate data computed by Hi-sAfe is passed to Sureau each day, then Sureau computes the hydraulic processes in the crop, and passes the daily averaged values of the state variables back to Hi-sAFe), we were able to compare the results of Hi-sAFe alone vs Hi-sAFe coupled with SUREAU. In the absence of extreme events, both models predict similar values of transpiration and water potential, indicating that despite very different formalisms, the simpler model (Hi-sAFe) correctly predicts crop functioning in normal conditions. However, comparison of results in conditions with an intense heat wave combined with a drought in April, shows that the SUREAU model predicts the death of the plant due to full embolism, while Hi-sAFe does not, thus overestimating the resilience of crops to heat waves. Simulations of more nuanced scenarios will allow determining the range of conditions in which agroforestry conditions buffer the microclimate and might bring resistance to the crop. This work is being carried out within the PhD thesis of Florian Soulard, who is currently preparing

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

a manuscript to present these results in a peer-reviewed journal. He already presented the coupling of the models in a poster at the EURAF conference in Brno in May 2024.

b) CO₂ effect on tree growth

To improve the ability of the model to predict the impact of climate change on agroforestry systems, we need to represent the fertilising effect of an increased atmospheric concentration on tree growth (the effect of CO₂ concentration on crops is already taken into account in STICS, on which **Hi-sAFe** is based to represent crops). We have finalised taking into account the effect of CO₂ on tree growth through an effect on Light Use Efficiency and on Water Use Efficiency, according to the equations presented in D2.5.

3.12.2 FAIRness improvement

Since March 2025, the Hi-sAFe code has been distributed as open source under the CC-BY license at <https://github.com/hisafe/hisafe>. In preparation for this, the JAVA code has been cleaned up and commented extensively to make it easier to upgrade by future developers:

- All variable names have been revised for clarity and understanding.
- All comments have been translated into English.
- Javadoc tags have been inserted to produce automatic code documentation, which is also available on GitHub.

The website has also been completely updated as well as the documentation associated with the latest version of the model. <https://www1.montpellier.inra.fr/wp-inra/hi-safe/en/>

The model installation and user manuals, as well as the list of all parameters and inputs/outputs, are available on GitHub and on the website.

3.12.3 Dissemination and exploitation

Exploitation has started within the project itself (cf metAlsaf above)

3.13 VOC'tool: characterising the chemical landscape and its effect on pests and beneficial arthropods

Following the development of a VOC capture instrument by the iteipmai (ACTA) teams, capture tests were carried out under controlled conditions to confirm the repeatability and robustness of the tool – consisting of a solid adsorbent into an insert, connected to a portable pump – and the method – including the VOC capture, extraction, and analysis steps – before transferring the tests to the field. Since the beginning of the project, 71 tests have been carried out. These tests were conducted by varying different parameters, such as temperature, pump flow rate, duration, type of adsorbent, number of adsorbents, and duplicates were performed. Unfortunately, the tests were inconclusive because the results were not repeatable from one test to another. As a result, iteipmai initiated a new bibliographic search to find new adsorbents that should be more suitable for the desired use. Following this research, an adsorbent that had not yet been tested as part of the DIGITAF project was put forward. New tests are currently being carried out at iteipmai to assess whether this adsorbent can produce repeatable results from one test to another, which is essential before the tool can be tested in the field.

3.14 CarboCatch: validating carbon certificates in agroforestry

The Tool CarboCatch was developed by the Louis Bolk Institute and Space4Good. CarboCatch is an online user-friendly tool for modelling carbon sequestered in aboveground biomass using a combination of field data, satellite data, and artificial intelligence (AI). The goal of the tool is to align

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

with carbon certification schemes to provide a reliable estimate of carbon certificates from agroforestry systems. The tool's unique selling point is that it minimises manual collection of the tree data, which is labour-intensive and costly, and is used for validating carbon certificates. The premise is that satellite data and AI can greatly reduce the monitoring & evaluation (M&E) costs, making agroforestry carbon farming much more lucrative. The second phase of tool development was executed in 2024, financed by a research project with local Dutch partners. In this phase, the tool was developed and tested for walnut trees in silvopastoral systems, and shows promising results with high model performance for predicting biomass. A report (in Dutch) on the current model's performance results is available upon request (w.thissen@louisbolk.nl). Currently the tool is not open source and not operational. This is because the tool developers are still looking for a suitable exploitation model for the tool beyond the initial development through two research projects. In the next phase, the tool should ideally be tested in a real-life pilot project aimed at generating carbon certificates with agroforestry. Also other agroforestry systems, such as fodder hedges, could be included in the tool, though reliable field data is required for this to be developed. The tool was not included for further testing and development within the DigitAF consortium at the start of the project. However, because the aim of the tool aligned well with the DigitAF project, the tool was presented to tool developers and LL leaders for feedback on the tool, sharing knowledge on how the tool works, and to gauge interest in the tool. Several LL leaders showed interest in the tool for their LL (CZ, DE, NL), but development steps are needed to make the tool operational for other EU countries. One major point is that the Netherlands has a unique position in the sense that high-resolution satellite data is made freely available by the government. If other member states make such data available for public use, CarboCatch could easily be adapted to other EU countries.

3.15 SCOPE: Remote sensing products to advance AF modelling

Remote sensing offers new ways to explore and monitor vegetation at large spatial and temporal scales. Reflectance (both thermal and optical) indices offer a rapid way to assess various parameters over large areas, increasing the capability to parameterise and validate empirical and mechanistic models, and extending their spatial-temporal scope, which were previously restricted to specific case studies. However, its application to the study and modelling of agroforestry systems (AFs) is still limited for multiple reasons, including spatial-temporal resolution and the inherent limitations of spectral information.

Despite the increase in spatial resolution (pixel size) of satellite images, this is still in the range of meters, especially in freely accessible products, which makes it impossible to separate the spectral signature of different plant components (and this in relation to the soil and shadows) in heterogeneous systems such as AFs. When horizontal heterogeneity is combined with vertical heterogeneity, with overlapping vegetation layers, as occurs in AFs, the spectral signal becomes even more confused, reflecting mainly that emitted by the top-of-canopy (TOC; the trees in AFs). The growth in the potential and availability of unmanned vehicles that can support hyperspectral cameras, thermal cameras, radars (LIDAR), etc., makes it possible to achieve the spatial resolution (on the cm scale) necessary for monitoring horizontally and/or vertically heterogeneous systems. However, in this case, the difficulty lies in achieving sufficient temporal resolution, which is particularly important for more dynamic systems, such as crops and pastures.

Despite all these limitations, remote sensing products have been mainly used to map and classify farmland trees and AFs at different scales and regions (e.g., Bolivar-Santamaría et al., 2021; Lu et al., 2022; Escobar-López et al., 2024; Chehreh et al., 2023; Usman et al., 2023; Kou et al., 2024). However,

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

remote sensing products can advance the development of numerical models related to AFs functioning in several ways. For instance, the vast availability of RS observations can be used to benchmark the outputs of process-based models. This approach is particularly common in land surface or ecosystem models. A common example is the benchmarking of simulated vegetation productivity using numerical models with Earth observation products, such as NPP or GPP derived from MODIS algorithms (Exbrayat et al., 2019). This approach has the advantage of offering direct real-world observations against which models could be compared, which can be particularly useful in places with difficult access and at large temporal scales. On the other hand, it also may introduce biases due to retrieval errors or extrapolation outside the observation ranges (Luo et al., 2012). Similarly, not only earth observation products can be used to benchmark model outputs, but also eddy-covariance data (Luo et al., 2012). In Table 5, we include some RS products that are commonly used to benchmark model simulations.

Table 5 Examples of RS products used to benchmark model simulations.

Products	Variables	Resolution Spatial	Time Temporal span	Source	
MODIS- MOD16A2	Total Evaporanspiration Potential	500 m	8-days	2021 present	https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/products/mod16a2v061/
MODIS MOD17A2H	Evapotranspiration Gross Primary Productivity	500 m	8-days	2021 present	
MODIS MOD15A2H	Leaf Area Index	500 m	8-days	2000 present	https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/products/mod15a2hv061/
Sentinel-1	Surface Moisture	Soil 1 km	daily	2014 present	https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/soil-presentmoisture/daily-surface-soil-moisture-v1.0
	Soil Water Index	1 km	daily	2015 present	https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/soil-presentmoisture/daily-soil-water-index-europe-v1-0-1km
Sentinel-2	Leaf Area Index Plant Phenology Index	10 m	daily	2016 present	https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/vegetation/high-resolution-leaf-area-index https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/vegetation/high-resolution-plant-phenology-index

Alternatively, the combination of RS products and model simulations through well-established statistical techniques (i.e. data-assimilation, DA) to obtain the best possible estimate and its uncertainty is also an important avenue of research in forest and crop modelling (Huang et al., 2019; Jin et al., 2018). This approach seeks to update the outputs of a calibrated model to match RS products to provide a corrected model output. One of the advantages of DA is the possibility of updating the model outputs as new RS data is generated. Knowling et al. (2023) successfully provided end-of-season yield estimates by continuously updating a crop model following a DA approach. The authors argued that this methodology could enhance decision support systems in agriculture by integrating real-time observations with existing knowledge. To the best of our knowledge, this approach has not been used in agroforestry systems.

Data assimilation has the potential to improve the predictive capacity of numerical models. However, it does not solve the problem of modelling complex interactions between agroforestry vegetation components, because a well-calibrated agroforestry model should be available. The need for a site-specific calibration might be particularly challenging in complex agroforestry systems. RS products can also facilitate the calibration of agroforestry models by integrating different data sources related to both crops or trees. For instance, crop phenology is a crucial variable to estimate yields in numerical

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

models. Deriving estimates of phenological stages based on RS products could help to parametrize crop dynamics. Fernández-Habas et al. (2025) gathered phenological stages from the MODIS Land Cover Dynamics (MCD12Q2) to calibrate the pasture layer to model also the Iberian dehesa using Hi-sAFe. Similar approaches can be used to approximate tree size and structure. Tree size is commonly derived from allometric equations based on the measurement of stem diameter at breast height. However, it cannot be assessed from RS products. To overcome this limitation, a new generation of allometric equations has been developed, where crown size and tree height are used to estimate tree size and carbon stocks (Jucker et al., 2017). Indeed, in the last years RS products have been helpful for the estimation of AGB of the upperstory layer in different AFS (e.g., Bolívar-Santamaría et al., 2021; Thapa et al., 2023, Kanmegne Tamga et al., 2023; Singh et al., 2024; Pegoraro Starlin et al., 2025). This unlocks the potential of using RS products to calibrate new tree species for use in agroforestry models. The retrieval of multiple plant functional traits (PFT) from RS products for ecosystem modelling is also in rapid progress. The tracking of physiologically driven signals, such as surface temperature, photochemical reflectance index (PRI), and sun-induced chlorophyll fluorescence (SIF) rely on reflected visible and infrared radiance and derived vegetation indices (VI) related to vegetation structure, biochemistry, and photosynthetic capacity that vary over medium time scales (Pacheco-Labrador et al., 2024).

Non-parametric methods (e.g. machine learning regression algorithms, random forest regressions, or neural networks) exploit the entire reflectance signal to model empirical linear and non-linear relationships with different PFT. RS-based vegetation indexes (Vis) are also widely used to predict PFT related to photosynthesis, plant water status and productivity (Montero et al., 2023). Both approaches, nevertheless, have multiple limitations for the spatial and temporal upscaling. In this regard, the inversion of Radiative Transfer Model (RTMs) is most suitable to retrieve PFT from heterogeneous canopies featured with the typical low spatial resolution of satellite images (Hornero et al., 2021). Among RTMs, SCOPE (Soil-Canopy Observation Photosynthesis and Energy) is especially suited to study vegetation function from RS observations (visible, thermal and SIF), as it couples several RTMs with energy balance and photosynthesis models (Soil-Vegetation-Atmosphere Transfer; SVAT models) (Pacheco-Labrador et al., 2021). Pacheco-Labrador et al. (2019) developed a multiple-constraint inversion approach of SCOPE able to retrieve vegetation biochemical, structural, as well as key functional traits, such as chlorophyll concentration (Cab), leaf area index (LAI), maximum carboxylation rate (Vcmax) and the Ball-Berry sensitivity parameter (m) in Iberian dehesas. Further on, Pacheco-Labrador et al. (2021) proposed a dual-leaf version of SCOPE to incorporate the spectral deviation caused by senescent pasture.

Surface energy balance models (SEB) have also been proven useful to estimate water fluxes in Iberian dehesas. These models estimate ET as the residual of the energy balance equation, based on variables as land surface temperature, albedo, and net radiation retrieved from remote sensing variables. Burchard-Levine et al. (2020) adapted the thermal-based two-source energy balance (TSEB) to the two-layered Iberian dehesas by considering phenological dynamics and assuming a dominant vegetation structure and cover (i.e., either grassland or broadleaved trees) for different seasons (TSEB-2S). TSEB-2S vastly improved over the default TSEB water and energy flux estimations. Similarly, Andreu et al. (2018) Integrated MODIS y LANDSAT images to simulate with a TSEB model the ET, vegetation ground cover, leaf area and phenology in Iberian dehesas. They assessed the tree contribution when the herbaceous layer was dry, assuming that the reflectance registered by the sensor corresponded only to the oaks and the constant behaviour across the year.

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

In summary, RS products have the potential to improve agroforestry modelling by either benchmarking model outputs, assimilating data to improve predictions dynamically or integrating various sources to aid in model parameterization through inversion of RTM to retrieve plant functional traits and identify key phenological stages. Recent advances in satellite technology are providing the opportunity to collect signals more closely related to dynamic vegetation properties and ecophysiological traits. These include hyperspectral Visible-Near InfraRed (VNIR) reflected radiance which enables the quantification of thermal infrared data for land surface temperature (LST), the Photochemical Reflectance Index (PRI), as well as solar-induced chlorophyll fluorescence (SIF) mapping. The European FLEX mission (FLuorescence EXplorer), expected for 2026, aims to make global measurements of fluorescence to gain a deeper understanding of how the photosynthesis process works and how photosynthesis affects the water and carbon cycles. Unlocking the full potential of these RS products can help improve the performance of agroforestry models and reduce the barriers to their applications.

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